

Linguistic Ellipsis in English: Analyzing Types and Functions of Elliptic Sentences

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Abstract. *This article analyzes linguistic ellipsis and elliptic sentences in English language, their types and study fields in order to produce a sentence fragment or an unfinished phrase, the ellipsis remnant of a syntactic omission is purposefully left grammatically defective or incomplete. This occurrence is known as ellipsis.*

Key words: *Ellipsis, three dots, omission, punctuation, dash, pause, brief pause, phrase, trailing off.*

An ellipsis, or *ellipses* in the plural form, is a punctuation symbol of three dots (. . .) that is familiar from Ancient Greek period that shows an omission of words, symbolize stop, break or suggests there is something left unsaid. An ellipsis can be used in a variety of ways, such as to intentionally leave out text or to imply a point without using words. Views on how to provide an ellipsis in printed materials differ, and they partially rely on the technology being utilized for display. Many technique guides are still influenced by the typewriter. Known casually as *dot, dot, dot*, the most popular technique among writers is the ellipsis, which can be used to indicate silence in a paragraph or, more practically, to indicate that a direct quote has been changed. Ellipses can be influential devices for writing. If you are aware how to perform them. We define ellipsis in further detail and describe how to use those three dots in writing below. Additionally, we resolve the ellipsis and ellipses controversy and provide numerous ellipsis examples to illustrate its application. The ellipsis (pronounced il-LIP-sis) is a type of punctuation that represents a pause or that something has been intentionally left out. Specifically, it shows that words have been cut from a direct quote, so the reader knows the original passage has been modified.

Three dots or periods make up the ellipsis in form. We like the version with spaces between the periods, however different style guides have varying rules for ellipses. When used within a quote [...] in professional writing and journalism, the ellipsis is enclosed in brackets to indicate that the editors, not the original speaker, added it. In terms of usage, the ellipsis is similar to the colon and dash, two additional punctuation marks. "Ellipsis in English Literature: Signs of Omission", Anne Toner suggests that the first use of the punctuation in the English language dates to a 1588 translation of Terence's *Andria*, by Maurice Kyffin.¹ In this case, however, the ellipsis consists not of dots but of short dashes. While the ellipsis and the dash both represent breaks in text, the dash—or more precisely, the "em dash"—represents an abrupt interruption. Although it is more forceful than the "soft" pause of an ellipse, the dash can also be used to indicate a pause. However, for far more purposeful purposes, the colon also signifies a textual break. A list, quotation, or explanation of what comes before it is introduced with a colon. However, unlike ellipses and dashes, they do not represent silence. Furthermore, neither the dash nor the colon can represent omitted words; only the ellipsis can

¹ Toner, Anne (2015). *Ellipsis in English Literature: Signs of Omission*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press. p. 151

do that. “Subpuncting” of medieval manuscripts also denotes omitted meaning and may be related.² It was occasionally employed to indicate expletives that would have otherwise been prohibited in pulp literature and other early 20th-century novels. An implied alternative that is indicated by context can also be implied by an ellipsis. For example, "I never drink wine ..." implies that the speaker does drink something else—such as vodka. Ellipsis can be seen in a variety of writing styles. For example, an ellipsis is employed in poetry to accentuate sarcasm or to get the reader to consider the poem's last themes. It can also be used as a thought-pause or line break at the caesura. In news reporting, often put inside square brackets, it is used to indicate that a quotation has been condensed for space, brevity or relevance, as in "The Governor said that [...] he would not be satisfied", where the exact quotation was "The Governor said that, for as long as this situation continued, he would not be satisfied". Ellipsis can signify a leading statement, an incomplete idea, a small pause, an echoing voice, or an uncomfortable or uneasy quiet, depending on the situation. Using an ellipsis to lead into stillness is known as silence.—for example: "But I thought he was..." When placed at the end of a sentence, an ellipsis may be used to suggest depression or longing.³ Additionally, ellipses may be used in place of paragraph breaks to divide items in lists in newspaper and magazine columns. When entire lines in a quoted poetry are omitted, writers and editors typically employ an ellipsis. According to “The Chicago Manual of Style”⁴ Any word, phrase, line, or paragraph that is left out of a quoted passage but not at the end is indicated by an ellipsis. To distinguish between omissions within a sentence (using three dots:...) and omissions between sentences (using a period and a space followed by three dots:...), ellipses are often employed in two ways. The first uses three dots for any omission. There is a lot of confusion over ellipsis and ellipses, but the truth is that they’re the same word. The singular is ellipsis, and the plural is ellipses. Because there are three dots involved, even this can be perplexing. Accordingly, numerous ellipses are two or more groups of three dots, but a single ellipsis is just one group of three dots. In linguistics, ellipses come in a variety of forms, but in writing, they serve four primary purposes. First of all, in writing, ellipsis is employed to eliminate words. Ellipses are used, usually from direct quotes, to indicate to the reader that words have been omitted. This is typically done to shorten the quote or to remove passages that are not pertinent to the subject. For instance, you can omit the middle portion and substitute it with an ellipsis if you wish to include the speaker's words at the start and finish of a quote but there is an extraneous portion in the center. For example:

(Original quote)

*It must be obvious, **from the very start**, that there is a contradiction in wanting to be perfectly secure in a universe whose very nature is momentariness and fluidity.*⁵

(Quote with ellipsis)

It must be obvious [. . .] that there is a contradiction in wanting to be perfectly secure in a universe whose very nature is momentariness and fluidity.

Make sure to choose the appropriate location when ellipsizing a quote to leave out a portion of it. Removing a portion that nevertheless leaves the rest of the sentence grammatically sound—as if nothing had been cut at all—is preferable. Since the omitted portion in the ellipsis example above fell between two commas, the statement is still coherent without it.

The second kind of ellipsis in literature is pause, which conveys tension or dramatic effect. For a dramatic effect, an ellipsis can also be used to indicate a brief pause or quiet in text. The ellipsis frequently appears before an expected passage, such as a joke's punchline. Building suspense before a major announcement is the goal. For instance:

2 McNabb, Cameron Hunt (17 August 2016). "The Mysterious History of the Ellipsis, From Medieval Subpuncting to Irrational Numbers". Slate. Archived from the original on 18 August 2016.

3 "Ellipsis". bookdesign.ca. 2011. Retrieved 29 April 2021.

4 The Chicago Manual of Style is a style guide for American English published since 1906 by the University of Chicago Press.

5 "The lazy mysticism of Alan Watts". *Philosophy for Life*. 1 June 2018.

“I am not sure... maybe we should wait and see “

The following kind of ellipsis is trailing off into the stillness; it gets progressively quieter and less assured until coming to a total stop. For a variety of reasons, humans occasionally leave sentences in speech unfinished. Perhaps our listeners already know what we are going to say, so we don't need to say it, or perhaps we forgot what we were going to say. An ellipsis is used in writing to indicate this occurrence. The speaker has trailed off before finishing a sentence or quote when an ellipsis appears at the conclusion. For example:

Would you like tea with sugar or ...

The final kind is to imply that there is more. An ellipsis is typically used as a dramatic device to indicate that there is more to come when it appears at the end of a whole phrase. The phrase to be continued... is among the most often used examples, where the ellipsis suggests that the story is not over yet. In the correct context, this may be a very effective storytelling tool. The reader is essentially challenged to predict and envision what will happen next, which heightens their excitement and draws them in more. Use it sparingly to avoid wasting its effect, but it works best for cliffhangers and other endings.

Finally, we can state that ellipsis A punctuation mark consisting of three dots (...) that indicates a pause, an omission of words, or anything left unsaid is called an ellipsis. An ellipsis at the start or end of a sentence indicates that something has been cut out or that there has been a pause, as if the speaker has trailed off. An ellipsis at the end of a sentence indicates that the tale is not finished. To let the reader know that something has been left out of a straight quote, use an ellipsis as a placeholder. Ellipses can also be used in storytelling to create suspense and give the reader something to ponder.

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